

Working Capital Turnover (WCT) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

Purpose - This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Working Capital Turnover (WCT) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review.

Research Method – Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the WCT ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the WCT ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the WCT ratio using a literature review study.

Findings – The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 89 journal publications regarding the WCT ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the WCT ratio are divided into 6 clusters and 130 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 19 topics around the WCT ratio.

Implication - The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around WCT ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Working Capital Turnover (WCT), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Working Capital Turnover (WCT) is a financial ratio used to measure how effectively a company is managing their working capital. This ratio measures how much income is generated by each unit of working capital owned by the company. In the banking context, working capital is the amount of assets used to finance the bank's daily operations, such as cash, securities, receivables, and inventory. The development of the use of the WCT ratio in banking has gone hand in hand with the development of the banking industry itself. In recent years, the banking industry has experienced significant changes, especially in terms of technology and competition. This has encouraged banks to focus more on the efficiency and effectiveness of their operations, including in terms of working capital management (Nasution, 2022).

In the banking context, the WCT ratio can provide useful information for management in managing their working capital. This ratio can help companies evaluate the efficiency of using their assets, such as inventory and receivables. Apart from that, this ratio can also help companies assess their financial performance, including their ability to pay debt and earn income. However, it is important to remember that the use of the WCT ratio in banking has several factors that need to be considered. For example, changes in the minimum capital requirements required by regulators may have an impact use of the WCT ratio in banking. Apart from that, increasingly fierce competition in the banking industry can also influence the use of the WCT ratio, because banks tend to focus more on their operational efficiency to win the competition (Hariasih, 2023).

Technological developments also influence the way banks manage their working capital, which can influence the use of the WCT ratio. Technology can help banks manage their working capital more efficiently and effectively, such as by automating operational processes and reducing operational costs. Overall, the use of the WCT ratio in banking continues to grow along with the development of the banking industry and will continue to be a useful tool for companies to manage their working capital and measure their financial performance. However, it should be remembered that factors such as changes in regulations, increasingly fierce competition and technological developments can influence the use of the WCT ratio in banking (Juniawan, 2022).

Research on WCT in banking continues to develop in line with the banking industry's need to measure and improve the efficiency and effectiveness of their working capital management. The following are some of the latest research developments regarding WCT in banking: first, research which aims to analyze the influence of bank size on WCT in banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) for the 2012-2016 period. The research results show that bank size has a significant positive effect on WCT, indicating that larger banks tend to be more effective in managing their working capital (Badera, 2018). Second, research that examines the relationship between WCT and bank financial performance in India uses data from 23 banks listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) for the 2012-2017 period. The research results show that WCT has a positive and significant influence on bank profitability, which shows that efficiency in working capital management can improve bank financial performance (Erick, 2019). Third, research aims to analyze the factors that influence WCT in banks in Indonesia. The research results show that profitability, liquidity and leverage have a significant positive effect on WCT, while bank age and asset growth do not have a significant effect on WCT (Pratiwi, 2020). Fourth, research aims to analyze the influence of WCT on performance Islamic banking finance in Indonesia uses data from 15 Islamic banks for the 2013-2017 period. The research results show that WCT has a significant positive influence on the profitability and growth of Islamic banking assets in Indonesia. Overall, research on WCT in banking continues to develop with a focus on its relationship with bank financial performance, factors that influence WCT, and the influence of bank size on WCT. This research has important implications for banking management in improving the efficiency and effectiveness of their working capital management to achieve better financial performance (Octaviani, 2021).

The aim of this research is to map research topics around the WCT ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publication of a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review studies to analyze, identify and review articles from journals Nationally accredited Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding WCT. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research WCT. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics surrounding the WCT ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Working Capital Turnover (WCT) is a ratio used to measure the efficiency of a bank in managing its working capital in creating income operational. This ratio calculates how much a bank's operating income is in one year compared to the working capital it has. Mathematically, the WCT formula is $\text{Operating Income} / \text{Working Capital}$. Operating income is calculated by adding up all the income earned by the bank in one year, such as interest from loans, fees and commissions, and other income. Meanwhile, working capital is calculated by subtracting short-term liabilities from current assets. Current assets include cash, marketable securities, and receivables, while short-term liabilities include accounts

payable, bank loans, and accrued expenses. The higher the WCT ratio, the more efficient the bank is in managing its working capital to generate operational income. However, it should also be noted that this ratio can be influenced by other factors such as interest rates and overall economic performance (Zuniarti, 2017).

Bibliometric studies are research methods that measure and analyze the quantity, quality and impact of literature or scientific publications contained in a particular scientific discipline or field. This method is used to evaluate research performance, track research trends, and understand the relationship between authors, journals, institutions, and research topics. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out by collecting data from bibliographic databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. The data collected can be in the form of number of publications, citation frequency, journal impact factor, citation speed, and so on. The data is then analyzed using statistical methods and visualization techniques to produce information that is useful in understanding research trends and making decisions based on scientific evidence. Bibliometric studies are very useful in assisting researchers, publishers, journal editors, and public policy in evaluating research performance, identifying trending research topics, and gaining insight into scientific developments within a discipline. Bibliometric studies can also be used to evaluate individual performance, such as measuring the productivity of authors, doctoral supervisors, and research institutions (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is software used for visualization and analysis of bibliometric data. This software can be used to analyze and extract information from bibliographic databases such as Scopus and Web of Science, then visualize that information in the form of diagrams and graphs. VOSviewer can be used to perform cluster analysis, keyword analysis, co-citation analysis, and network analysis based on citations. This software can also allow users to visualize the relationships between publications, authors, journals, keywords, and research institutions. The visualizations produced by VOSviewer are usually in the form of network maps or diagrams, which can help users understand research trends and relationships between entities in a particular research field. VOSviewer is very useful for researchers, publishers, journal editors, and public policy in evaluating research performance, identifying trending research topics, and gaining insight into scientific developments in a scientific discipline. This software can also help in predicting the direction and focus of future research, as well as providing a better view on future scientific developments (van Eck NJ, 2022).

literature review study is a research method carried out by carrying out critical analysis of existing literature or scientific publications in a particular research field. The purpose of a literature review study is to gain a deeper understanding of the research topic being researched, identify knowledge gaps in the field, and evaluate the progress of the research that has been carried out. Literature review studies are usually carried out by searching for and reviewing literature that is relevant to the research topic being studied, then organizing and analyzing the information found. The information is then synthesized to produce a more complete understanding of the research topic. The literature review process involves critical reading and evaluation of the literature, including evaluation of research methodology, accuracy of data, and relevance of the literature to the research topic. Literature reviews are often used in qualitative research and scientific research, and can be used as a stand-alone research method or as part of a larger research process. Literature review studies are very useful in helping researchers to understand the theoretical and empirical context of research topics, and gain a more complete understanding of research that has been conducted previously. Literature review studies can also be used to identify knowledge gaps in a particular research area and provide directions for future research (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Working Capital Turnover (WCT). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about WCT in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Tool Data analysis using Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category including the key words " Working Capital Turnover " and "WCT" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding WCT using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around WCT using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around WCT using a literature review study (Rohimah et al., 2023).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications regarding Working Capital Turnover (WCT) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 89 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2010 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about WCT by year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2010	2	2016	1	2020	20
2013	1	2017	3	2021	14
2014	4	2018	9	2022	16
2015	7	2019	10	2023	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Working Capital Turnover (WCT) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Article search results in the Perish/Harzing software are exported in format RIS (Research Information Systems), then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 5 consists of 16 topic items, namely: capital, cost, determination, empirical study, equity, f test, level, manufacturing company, problem, profit, rest, roe, spss version, stock exchange, t test, turnover.
- Cluster 6 consists of 7 topic items, namely: beverage sector, determination test, effectiveness, firm value, hypothesis, h testing, multiple linear regression.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Working Capital Turnover (WCT) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Based on a review of literature reviews in previous research journals, researchers found 15 research topics regarding the WCT ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking. that is:

First, the influence of the Current Ratio on WCT. WCT and Current Ratio (CR) are two different but interrelated financial ratios in banking financial performance analysis. WCT measures how efficiently a company utilizes working capital in generating income. WCT is calculated by dividing operating income by working capital. The higher the WCT, the more efficient the company is in utilizing working capital to generate income. Meanwhile, the Current Ratio (CR) measures the company's ability to meet short-term obligations with the current assets it owns. CR is calculated by dividing current assets by short-term liabilities. The higher the CR, the better the company's ability to meet short-term obligations. In the banking context, WCT and CR have an impact on company liquidity and solvency. Liquidity relates to the company's ability to pay short-term obligations, while solvency relates to the company's ability to pay long-term obligations. The relationship between WCT and CR in banking is as follows:

(1) The higher the WCT, the more efficient the company is in utilizing working capital to generate income. This can increase revenue and can also strengthen the company's ability to meet short-term obligations, because the company has more reliable current assets. Therefore, high WCT can increase CR in banking. (2) However, if the WCT is too high, it could indicate that the company is not utilizing working capital optimally. Conversely, a company may have too much unproductive working capital. This can reduce the rate of return on capital and can worsen the company's liquidity. Therefore, a WCT that is too high can reduce CR in banking. Thus, WCT and CR influence each other in the banking context. However, the relationship between the two is not always linear and can change depending on the company's financial situation. Therefore, it is important for companies to conduct a careful analysis of these two ratios to understand their impact on financial performance and make informed business decisions.

Second, the influence of financial distress on WCT. Financial Distress is a condition where a company faces financial difficulties and is unable to fulfill its financial obligations at the specified time. In the banking industry, WCT can be interpreted as a bank's ability to manage liquidity and credit. The higher the WCT ratio, the more efficient the bank is in managing working capital and the greater the bank's ability to provide credit. However, if this ratio is too high, it could indicate that the bank is experiencing liquidity difficulties or does not have sufficient capital reserves to face high credit risks. The influence of WCT on financial distress in banking can vary depending on financial conditions and the banking business itself. If a bank has a high WCT ratio and can generate stable income, then the bank will be better able to avoid financial distress. However, if a bank is too aggressive in providing credit and ignores credit risks, the bank can face financial distress even though it has a high WCT ratio. In addition, changes in market conditions, such as rising interest rates or falling stock prices, can affect a bank's financial performance and cause financial distress, regardless of its WCT ratio. Therefore, although the WCT ratio can provide an indication of the efficiency of working capital management and the potential for financial distress in banking, other factors also need to be considered in financial analysis and risk management in companies.

Third, the influence of share prices on WCT. WCT can provide an overview of how effectively a company uses its assets to generate revenue. The influence of WCT on share prices in banking can vary depending on market conditions and other factors that influence it. However, in general, banking companies that have a high WCT demonstrate a better ability to manage their working capital and generate higher income. When banking companies are able to manage their working capital well, this can improve their financial performance and increase company value, which in turn can have a positive impact on share prices. In addition, investors tend to be more interested in banking companies that are able to generate stable and consistent income from their working capital. However, the influence of WCT on share prices in banking must also be considered with other factors that influence the company's financial performance, such as economic conditions, industry competition and government regulations. Therefore, a more comprehensive analysis and other factors need to be considered to obtain a more complete picture of the influence of WCT on share prices in banking companies.

Fourth, the influence of financial performance on WCT. WCT can be calculated by dividing revenue by the total working capital owned by the company. In the banking industry, WCT can provide an overview of a bank's efficiency in managing its short-term assets and liabilities such as cash, securities, deposits and loans. The higher a bank's WCT, the more efficient the bank is in utilizing its working capital to generate income. In general, a high WCT can indicate that a company is able to generate more revenue with less working capital, meaning the bank can maximize the use of available resources to generate revenue. However, it should be noted that a WCT that is too high can also indicate that the bank is not exploiting the available growth potential and is focusing too much on managing its short-term assets. Apart from that, WCT can also affect bank liquidity. A low WCT may indicate that the bank is unable to utilize available resources efficiently and may lead to liquidity problems in the future. Therefore, banks need to find a balance between efficiency and liquidity by considering optimal WCT. Overall, WCT can provide an overview of bank efficiency and liquidity. However, it is important to consider other factors such as credit risk, operational costs and return on capital to get a more complete picture of a bank's financial performance.

Fifth, the influence of company performance on WCT. The higher the WCT ratio, the better the company's performance in utilizing working capital to obtain sales. In the banking context, WCT can be measured by comparing net interest income with the total working capital used to generate that income. The higher the WCT ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating net interest income with limited use of working capital. In the long term, a high WCT ratio can positively influence company performance because it can increase profitability and operational efficiency. However, it is worth noting that a very high WCT ratio can also indicate that the company is not investing enough working capital to gain greater sales. In addition, keep in mind that banking performance is also influenced by other factors such as liquidity, asset quality, credit risk and effective risk management. Therefore, it is important to consider the WCT ratio along with other ratios and other factors when assessing banking performance.

Sixth, the influence of liquidity on WCT. Liquidity is a company's ability to meet its short-term financial obligations. In the banking context, WCT can affect liquidity because banks use working capital to provide loans and finance their operational activities. If the WCT is high, it means the bank can generate more income with the same or less working capital. This can increase bank liquidity because the bank has more cash available to meet its short-term financial obligations. However, if the WCT is low, it means the bank cannot generate sufficient income with the working capital it has. This can affect the bank's liquidity because the bank may not have enough cash to meet its short-term financial obligations. Thus, WCT can have a positive or negative effect on banking liquidity depending on how efficient the bank is in managing its working capital. Banks that can use their

working capital efficiently to generate higher income will tend to have better liquidity. Conversely, banks that are inefficient in managing their working capital will tend to have worse liquidity.

Seventh, the influence of Net Profit Margin/NPM on WCT. NPM is the ratio of net profits generated by a company from each dollar of sales. In the banking industry, WCT refers to how quickly a bank can manage and convert cash and short investments into income. Meanwhile, NPM measures a bank's net profit as a percentage of total revenue. In relation to the influence of WCT on NPM, if banks can manage their working capital more efficiently, then banks can increase income and can also minimize operational costs. Thus, a high WCT can have a positive impact on NPM, because banks can generate greater profits from their income. However, keep in mind that a very high WCT can also indicate that the bank is not managing its working capital well, especially if the bank maintains inventory that is too low or does not have enough receivables to support its business operations. Therefore, banks must maintain a balance between high WCT and high NPM to ensure good financial health.

Eighth, the influence of company value on WCT. In the banking context, WCT can be used to measure a company's efficiency in managing and utilizing working capital such as cash, receivables and inventory. The higher the WCT, the more efficient the company is in managing its working capital and the higher the possibility of the company generating profits. WCT can influence company value in banking. If WCT increases, there will be an increase in company revenue and profitability, which can increase company value. In addition, a higher WCT also indicates that the company is more efficient in managing its working capital, which can improve the company's image in the eyes of investors and financial markets. However, it should be remembered that the influence of WCT on company value cannot be seen separately. There are other factors such as interest rates, market liquidity, government regulations, and economic conditions that can affect the value of companies in banking. Therefore, companies need to consider all these factors in making investment decisions and managing their working capital.

Ninth, the influence of profit growth on WCT. Profit growth is the percentage growth in net profit between two time periods. In the banking industry, WCT can influence profit growth in several ways: (1) Working capital management efficiency: If a company is able to manage working capital more efficiently, then this can free up resources and increase profits that can be reinvested. (2) Effect on costs: In the banking industry, costs Working capital such as interest on deposits and current liabilities can affect operational costs. The higher the WCT, the lower the working capital costs, thereby increasing net profits. (3) Credit growth: WCT can also influence bank credit growth. If a company is able to manage working capital more efficiently, this can free up resources that can be used to provide new credit, which can ultimately increase revenue and profits. In conclusion, WCT can influence profit growth in banking. The higher the WCT, the more efficient the management of working capital, so that it can increase net profits and accelerate credit growth. However, it is important to note that other factors such as economic conditions and competition can also influence banking company profit growth.

Tenth, the influence of income smoothing practices on WCT. Income smoothing is a practice carried out by companies to stabilize annual profits by shifting income or costs from one year to the next. The influence of WCT on income smoothing practices in banking can vary depending on the business strategy and company objectives. However, in general, the higher the WCT, the more difficult it is to practice income smoothing/income smoothing. This is due to the fact that banks, as financial institutions, depend on working capital to generate income. If a company has a high level of WCT, it means that the company is able to manage working capital well so that it is able to obtain higher income. On the other hand, if a company has a low WCT level, this means that the company may have difficulty generating sufficient income to cover its operational costs. In situations like this, companies may tend to practice income smoothing to cover the income shortfall.

However, even though companies have a high level of WCT, they can still practice income smoothing if there is a desire to generate stable profits. This practice is usually carried out to maintain company performance stable and avoid fluctuations that could disrupt investor and stakeholder confidence. Therefore, the influence of WCT on income practices Profit smoothing in banking needs to be analyzed carefully by considering various other factors that can influence business strategy and company goals.

Eleventh, the influence of Return On Assets/ROA on WCT. In the banking industry, WCT is usually calculated as the ratio between operating income and total assets owned. The higher the WCT ratio, the better the company's performance in utilizing working capital to generate income. At the same time, ROA reflects the company's ability to generate profits from the assets owned. The higher the ROA, the better the company's performance in generating profits from its assets. In the banking industry, a high WCT can increase ROA because the higher the WCT ratio, the better the company's performance in managing working capital to generate income. In this way, the company can increase the profits generated from the assets it owns. However, keep in mind that the relationship between WCT and ROA is not always positive. There are situations where a company with a high WCT ratio may face higher credit risk, which can have a negative impact on ROA. Therefore, it is important for companies to maintain a balance between operational efficiency and risk management to achieve optimal financial performance.

Twelfth, the influence of Return On Equity /ROE on WCT. The influence of Working Capital Turnover (WCT) on Return On Equity (ROE) in banking can be seen as follows: (1) Effectiveness of working capital management: If banking companies are able to manage their working capital well and generate high sales, then they will have WCT tall one. This will allow companies to generate greater profits from the capital held by their shareholders, so that their ROE will increase. (2) Low credit risk: If banking companies can manage their working capital well, they will can effectively settle their short-term obligations, such as short-term loans. This will help reduce the credit risks faced by companies and will ultimately strengthen their financial position, which in turn will increase ROE. (3) Operational efficiency: WCT can also reflect the company's operational efficiency level. If companies can manage their working capital efficiently, they may be able to improve their operational efficiency. This will help them reduce operational costs and increase their profit margins, which will ultimately increase ROE. However, it should be noted that WCT should not always be interpreted as a good performance indicator. A high WCT can indicate that a company is being too aggressive in their working capital management, which can lead to higher credit risk and eventual losses. Therefore, companies need to pay attention to risk factors that may be related to their WCT levels and pay careful attention to the relationship between WCT and ROE.

Thirteenth, the influence of Return On Investment/ROI on WCT. In banking, WCT and ROI are interrelated because the efficient use of working capital can influence the profits obtained from investments. The higher the WCT, the more efficiently the company uses working capital, which ultimately can increase ROI. However, a WCT that is too high can also indicate that a company is not investing their working capital effectively, as they may be holding too much inventory or outstanding receivables. This can impact ROI negatively because working capital is tied up in unproductive assets. Therefore, banks must consider the balance between WCT and ROI to achieve efficient use of working capital and optimal profits from investments.

Fourteenth, the influence of stock returns on WCT. The influence of WCT on stock returns in banking can be seen from the perspective of two things, namely risk and profitability. In terms of risk, companies with low WCT tend to have lower risk, as they use more working capital to support their operations. In contrast, companies with high WCT tend to have higher risks, because they rely on less working capital to run their operations. Therefore, companies with a low WCT may be attractive to investors looking for a more stable and safe investment, while companies with a high

WCT may be more attractive to investors looking for higher potential returns. In terms of profitability, companies with high WCT tend to have the potential to generate higher profits, because they can generate more sales with less working capital. However, companies with low WCT may have higher profit margins, because they invest more working capital into their operations. In the banking industry, WCT can influence stock returns because banks need working capital to run their operations. A bank with a low WCT may rely on more working capital to support its operations, which can result in higher profit margins but lower risk. On the other hand, banks with high WCT can achieve higher operational efficiency, but can also increase credit and operational risks. Therefore, it is important for investors to consider the WCT ratio along with other factors when choosing a bank to invest in. In addition, WCT is not the only factor that influences stock returns, and other factors such as risk management, profit growth, and cash flow must also be considered.

Fifteenth, the influence of profitability on WCT. In the banking industry, WCT can have a significant influence on profitability. The higher the WCT, the better the company can manage and utilize the working capital it has to generate income. In this case, the more efficient the company is in managing its working capital, the greater the possibility of creating added value for the company shareholders and increase profitability. However, it should be remembered that the influence of WCT on banking profitability cannot be measured separately. There are many other factors that also influence banking financial performance, such as operational costs, credit risk, interest rates, and other macroeconomic factors. Therefore, WCT should be analyzed along with other financial ratios to assess a company's overall financial performance.

Sixteenth, tools for understanding WCT. Before you can understand the working capital turnover ratio, you must first understand what working capital is. Working capital refers to the money available to a business to spend on essential payments, operations, etc. After all bills and debt installments have been paid. Every business needs working capital to keep things running smoothly between payments from clients or customers. There are many ways for startups to manage working capital needs, such as: (1) Building capital reserves into the budget: Keeping money set aside in a bank account to help your business manage the normal fluctuations of your cash flow cycle. These funds often take the form of raising equity or long-term venture capital debt. As startups grow, their working capital needs tend to grow along with them. This means you need to set aside increasingly large capital reserves. (2) Factoring receivables: factoring receivables simply means that you sell your receivables to banks or other financial service providers to increase your cash flow. What you do is get your invoice paid now and then send the invoice to the factoring company. However, keep in mind that factoring costs an additional 2% each month plus other fees. Factoring companies typically contact your customers directly to verify any underlying sales. (3) Securing working capital credit: With working capital credit, businesses have capital reserves to draw from revolving working capital. You can withdraw funds to pay for regular business operations when you need them and only pay back the capital when you take it and only for as long as you take it. It is an affordable, flexible financing solution and a low-cost alternative to venture capital debt or equity.

Seventeenth, how to calculate WCT. Before calculating the working capital turnover ratio, you must first know the amount of working capital the company has. To calculate working capital, take the total current assets and subtract the total current liabilities. These two figures must appear on the company's balance sheet and financial reports. For example, if a company has \$500,000 in current assets and \$300,000 in total current liabilities, then the amount of working capital is \$200,000. After knowing the amount of working capital, divide the total net sales for a year by the amount of working capital in the same year. The resulting figure is the working capital turnover ratio. It shows how many times it uses working capital to generate income during one year. The higher this ratio, the more efficient the business is in meeting short-term debt. A high ratio helps a company's operations run smoothly

and limits the need to raise additional funding. The formula is: Working Capital Turnover Ratio = Net Annual Sales/(Total Assets – Total Liabilities). To provide context and see why this metric is so important for measuring business efficiency. For example, company X had net sales of \$500,000 last year and working capital of \$50,000. Company On the other hand, company Y has sales of \$500,000 and working capital of \$125,000. This means they have a working capital turnover ratio of 4. Company Y only uses its working capital four times during the year to generate the same level of sales as company X.

Eighteenth, evaluate the working capital turnover ratio. It is not surprising that the higher this ratio the better. The more sales you can generate per dollar of working capital spent, the better the situation. Usually It is considered a good thing to allocate working capital more times a year to obtain annual net sales figures. This means easy money flowing in and out of the business and working to make more money. In the example above, Company X's working capital does the same thing. This working capital actually works for the company. This working capital works for the company 10 times a year. Company Y's working capital only works four times. Looking at the surface, both companies have generated the same amount of sales. It seems that money from Company X works harder than money from Company Y. How do you know if it has a high working capital turnover ratio? The working capital turnover ratio is considered high when it is higher than the turnover ratio of similar companies in the same industry. Using competitors' turnover ratios is a good benchmark because these companies generally sell products and have similar business structures. If the three closest competitors have working capital turnover ratios of 5, 4, and 6 respectively, and we have a ratio of 7, it is considered high because it exceeds the competitors.

Nineteenth, the benefits of a high WCT ratio. In general, a high working capital turnover ratio can provide a Competitive Advantage for a business. Because this ratio shows that working capital is being used more each year, it means money is flowing in and out of the business properly. This provides more spending flexibility and helps avoid financial problems. If demand for the product increases, there will be no shortage of inventory that sometimes occurs with increased sales. However, if the working capital turnover ratio is too high, it may be misleading. At first glance, it looks as if it is operating at very high efficiency. However, the reality may be that working capital is so low that the business will run out of funds. Suppose Company Z finished the year with sales of \$2.1 million and had working capital of \$200,000 and \$400,000 at the beginning and end of the year. This means that Company Z has average working capital of \$300,000. As a result, the working capital turnover ratio is 7. Now, assume Company A also finishes the year with sales of \$2.1 million but has average working capital of only \$50,000. This results in a ratio of 42 which is far too large for the industry. This puts the business at risk of running out of funds even though ratios show they are doing better than competitors. The working capital turnover ratio can also be misleading if the company has very high Accounts Payable. This may indicate that the company is having difficulty paying its bills on time.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the number of research publications regarding the Working Capital Turnover (WCT) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 2010 to 2023 originating from national journals indexed by Google Scholar and accredited by Sinta, there were 89 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results around the WCT ratio in Sharia Banking and Conventionally divided into 6 clusters and 130 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 36 topics, cluster 2 consists of 28 topics, cluster 3 consists of 23 topics, cluster 4 consists of 20 topics, cluster 5 consists of 16 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 7 topics. Third, based on mapping literature review studies, there are 19 topics regarding the WCT ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: the influence of the current ratio, financial distress, stock prices, financial

performance, company performance, liquidity, Net Profit Margin (NPM), company value, profit growth, income smoothing practices, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return On Investment/ROI, stock returns, profitability of WCT, tools in understanding WCT, how to calculate WCT, evaluating working capital turnover ratios, and the benefits of a high WCT ratio.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that it can The following research results were obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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